

9. England Clarifies its Agroforestry Basic Payment Rules

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EURAF is an NGO, based in Montpellier and Brussels (Transparency Register ID of [913270437706-82](https://www.transparencyregister.eu/roa/individual/913270437706-82)). It aims "to promote the adoption of agroforestry practices across Europe by supporting efforts to develop awareness, education, research, policy making and investments which foster the use of trees on farms". It has a network of 31 affiliated entities in 23 countries (see euraf.net).

England has clarified that areas of agroforestry are eligible for Basic Payments as long as the the agricultural activity is "predominant" - i.e. covering at least 50% of the land area underneath the tree canopy.

On the 9th December 2021 the English Rural Payments Agency clarified its rules for basic payments to agroforestry systems. The existing [Basic Payment Scheme Rules](#) for 2020 (England) state that ...

Parcels containing trees remain **eligible** for payments if they are:

- A. individual trees scattered within an agricultural parcel;
- B. lines of trees (of a maximum of two trees wide) on an agricultural parcel;
- C. groups of trees on an agricultural parcel that are not adjacent to a boundary; and
 - a. the area underneath the canopy is used for **agricultural activity** (this condition is met where it is **suitable** for cultivation or grazing of livestock);
 - b. more than **50% of the area** underneath the tree canopy is covered by grasses, other herbaceous forage or arable land.

or

- D. groups of trees on an agricultural parcel that are adjacent to a boundary and;
 - a. the area underneath the canopy is used for agricultural activity (this condition is met where it is suitable for cultivation or grazing of livestock);
 - b. if unsuitable for cultivation, the entire area under the canopy is accessible to farm animals for grazing; and
 - c. more than 50% of the area underneath the tree canopy is covered by grasses, other herbaceous forage or arable land.

All other groups of trees are "ineligible woodland". Areas of land set-aside for woodland creation under Agri Environment or national woodland scheme, including National Forest Changing Landscape Scheme, Woodland Carbon Fund may still attract BPS payments if specific conditions are met.

Despite the [clear advantages of agroforestry](#) in England, confusion has remained over the eligibility of agroforestry for Basic Payments. Thus, English Rural Payments Agency¹ issued the Guidance Note ([Agroforestry and the Basic Payment Scheme](#)) for clarification. It contains some encouraging statements and photos about agroforestry. "**Agroforestry**" is

... where trees are deliberately combined with agriculture on the same piece of land. It plays an important role in creating woodland on farms. It's an essential bridge between agriculture and forestry, providing two potential sources of income to farmers: a) the agricultural products (livestock or crops); b) forestry-generated products (sawlogs, fuelwood, fruit and nuts). This diversity will help reduce the risk from changes in the agricultural markets and help to stimulate and strengthen the rural economy.

Agroforestry also supports a number of goals in the government's 25 Year Environment Plan and Clean Growth Strategy. It provides wider ecosystem services, such as increased production potential, soil conservation, carbon capture, improved livestock welfare and increased biodiversity, and habitat creation. Agroforestry can also play an important role in climate change mitigation and adaptation. The Committee

¹ These comments relate only to England: Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland have their own rules

on Climate Change estimates that agroforestry (specifically: a) silvoarable systems - where crops grow between trees, b) silvopastoral systems - where farm animals graze between trees, c) hedge creation) could result in carbon emissions savings of 5.9 MtCO₂e per year by 2050. This represents approximately 13% of the total current emissions from the agriculture sector. Current ongoing research commissioned by Defra is also assessing the potential carbon savings from agroforestry, the results of this work are expected to be published early 2021. The government is looking at a wide range of agroforestry practices including: silvopasture, silvoarable, riparian forest buffers, windbreaks/shelterbelts, **forest farming** (including orchards), hedgerows with standards

Types of agroforestry that “may be compatible” with English BPS rules

Silvoarable (trees and crops). Trees that are planted at wide spacings and intercropped with a cereal or bioenergy crop.

Silvopasture (trees and livestock). Trees that are combined with forage grassland and livestock production.

Riparian Forest Buffer Trees that are planted between agricultural land and watercourses such as streams, rivers and lakes to act as buffers to protect the water quality.

Windbreak/Shelterbelt Trees that are planted in a linear format on the edge of a field to reduce wind speed, protect crops and livestock and reduce erosion

Comments

This new English “Guidance Note” on agroforestry is welcomed by EURAF. It does not change the existing rules, but shows that Member States always had significant “subsidiarity” in interpreting the EU guidelines for BPS eligibility.

However some of the terms used in the Guidance Note (e.g. “forest farming (including orchards)”) are confusing and

Tree Location	Agroforestry System	Type of “Land”	
		Agricultural Land	Forest Land
Trees inside parcels	Silvopastoral agroforestry	1 Wood pasture	9 Forest grazing
	Silvoarable agroforestry	2 Tree alley cropping 3 Coppice alley cropping 4 Multi-layer tree-gardens	10 Multi-layer tree gardens
	Permanent crop agroforestry	5 Orchard intercropping, 6 Orchard grazing.	
	Agro-silvo-pasture	7 Alternating cropping and grazing	
Trees between parcels	Tree Landscape Features (protected by CAP Conditionality Rules)	8 Tree-Landscape-Features: (protected hedges, scattered individual trees, trees in line, small groups of trees)	
Trees in settlements	Urban agroforestry	homegardens, allotments, etc.	

we commend the **EURAF Agroforestry Typology** to the UK..